

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

WHERE IS UKRAINE'S PLACE IN THE SITUATION OF BREAKING THE WORLD ORDER?

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Abstract

The article describes circumstances, which influence Ukraine and all human civilization. Even before Russian aggression, the situation in the world caused concerns among the progressive stratum of society, who perceive themselves as part of the civilized world.

Putin's Russia's aggression against Ukraine seems to sum up the "disease" of civilization with egocentrism, which is accompanied by disregard for universal morality, democratic order and international law.

Authors propose several steps to solve this situation to a benefit for Ukraine and all world's society.

Keywords: Russia's aggression, egocentrism, spiders in a jar, humane word civilization, happiness.

Urgency of the problem. Due to external and internal circumstances, Ukraine found itself at the epicenter of world events. Even before Russia's aggression, and its too much ambitious leader, the situation in the world caused concerns among the progressive stratum of society, who perceive themselves as part of the civilized world. Large-scale thinking people are characterizing this period as follows: "When, if not in the twentieth century, the most terrible mass murders took place, when people were purposefully and cold-bloodedly destroyed, including using bacteriological weapons. It was in the twentieth century that terrorism against innocent people was born... So, our planet is burdened with a large number of crises... Will we wait for a catastrophe of apocalyptic proportions (self-destruction) before we act?" [1, c. 200].

Presentation of the main material of the study.

Putin's Russia's aggression against Ukraine seems to sum up the "disease" of civilization with egocentrism, which is accompanied by disregard for universal morality, democratic order and international law.

This aggression shown that the world is in a state of "spiders in a jar" or "law of the jungle", and has a highly probable prospect of apocalypse, at least in terms of the self-destruction of modern human civilization. Authors agree with words of the famous thinker Yuval Noah Harari that "today the world order resembles a house in which everyone lives, but no one wants to repair it. Thus, the house will last for some time, but in the end it will collapse and then we will find ourselves in the jungle again, in a state of war of all against all" [5].

What globally threatens humanity? According to the authors, one of the key threats is the inability for most people to unite to get happiness through self-realization in all spheres of life. We are talking about the disunity of humanity in the face of a climatic and social catastrophe. There is only one way to counteract this, as proposed by the great strategist of our time, Lee

Kuan Yew, – by joint efforts to defeat disunity and find means to counteract threats [2].

But it is difficult to do this, because the disunity of people is facilitated by our nature, part of which is egocentrism and sociopathy, which is especially pronounced in leading politicians who consider themselves the leaders of civilization. These character traits are inherent in many people, but their pronounced expression in politicians encourages their development in ordinary people. A consumerist approach, the absence of a core of universal morality (and even uselessness, an obstacle to achieving success – author's note), which is based on people's respect for each other and for the natural environment, is spreading.

But what do all the people of the world desire? According to the authors, this is a desire for happiness. In this article, we will understand the concept of "happiness" as a state of mental comfort for a long period. Such a state can be achieved through the self-realization of each person and the satisfaction of his needs (of course, not all that come to the mind of a particular person, because Paradise on Earth is, objectively, impossible - author's note). But human civilization must, at least, strive to satisfy such needs of each person that do not harm other people. The self-realization of a mentally healthy person does not imply "moving over heads". The degree of probability of achieving this goal depends on two factors - external (including the actions of authorities) and internal - each person's understanding of himself - his own and universal moral values, his own character, professional qualities, etc.

Human capital is the only thing that creates additional value, turning the object of labor into the result of labor, with the use of professional, including creative, abilities. Therefore, we propose to consider certain areas of human capital application.

If we consider any society, nation or group of individuals, we can see four areas of its organization: political, economic, social, and cultural. All these areas

are made up of people "armed" with certain qualifications and technologies.

The primacy of human activity has been proven by many scientists, from A. Smith to K. McConnell and S. Brew. The latter two noted that, "Economics is the study of human behavior in the process of production, distribution and consumption" [3]. The classic of management Peter Drucker also concluded that "economic results are not the product of the action of some economic forces. They are achieved by man" [4]. The outstanding statesman of our time, Lee Kuan Yew, argued that "the quality of human resources is the only and very important factor that determines the competitiveness of countries... The key to innovation and technology is people."

At the same time, Lee Kuan Yew concluded that economic crises are also provoked by certain actions of people [2].

If we talk about social crises that have the potential to develop into devastating wars (perhaps even on a global scale), according to the authors, their human origin is obvious. Such situations arise when a certain category of people (sociopaths – author's note), who are in power at the national or territorial level, decides to take into their own hands additional resources, at the expense of others, change their values, including even religious preferences of other nations, etc.

If we talk about almost any threatening consequences, then they depend, first of all, on the actions of government officials, their ability to manage new opportunities for the benefit of people, or vice versa, ignoring their interests.

Each person must be considered as a person and at the same time as the main productive force of society. But the combination of human and professional qualities can worsen the competencies of an individual, and can improve them if all human abilities are realized in the conditions of a culture of system management with a focus on the final result.

Ukraine is the geographical center of Europe and one of the key suppliers of agricultural products to the world. And where is Ukraine's place in the situation of breaking the "world order"?

The development of post-war Ukraine cannot be unrelated to events in the world. For Ukraine to become on the civilizational rails of development, it is necessary to radically improve its state structure. For example, due to:

- combining the interests of the government and people, under public control;
- transition of power structures to a culture of systemic management, focusing on the final – human-centric – results;
- formation of peacekeeping education, by focusing on the development of the best human qualities, etc.

Such powerful social technologies have already been developed in Ukraine, using qualimetric digitalization [6]. These innovative technologies can add an

impetus to the improvement of managerial culture also in other countries, in the context of the development of a harmonious, humane world civilization. Therefore, in any, even the worst, times, there is a chance for salvation.

Conclusions and suggestions. According to the authors, the key reason for the disunity of humanity is the lack of a single unifying core - a landmark for the development of civilization. We are talking about a re-orientation to increase the level of happiness of people in all countries of the world, with understanding that this happiness is not achieved at the expense of the destruction of people around, or the environment.

Currently, happiness is threatened by a climate catastrophe and social upheaval, which, among other things, can lead to the development of local wars into a global world confrontation. Humanity can avoid this. But on one condition – if people will unite around one thing that is extremely important for each individual and at the same time for everyone. We are talking about the happiness of people on planet Earth as a resultant indicator of the actions of government structures at all levels (local, national, and supranational).

In this sense, the authors suggest taking a closer look at the developments of scientists from the Intellect Club for Civilizational Development of Ukraine in the context of familiarization with the grounded New Human-Centered Management Course for the Development of Post-War Ukraine [6]. It is this course that has the potential to save humanity from self-destruction.

And Ukraine has a chance to become the leader of this movement.

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